

D3.1

EMPOWER
 deliverables
Deliverable name**FIRST PROTOTYPE OF THREE GAMES****Type****DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype.****Dissemination level****PU - Public****Date****6**

This deliverable is the first prototype of the project, which includes the first three games defined in WP2 implemented for their first test with teacher and children. It will be the result of the first iteration of the project and will allow the start of different tasks of WP3 and WP4.

Description

WP.3

Work Package. 3

Lead Beneficiary – UVEG

FIRST PROTOTYPE OF THREE GAMES

Executive Summary

This document describes recent work developed by EMPOWER partners involved in WP2 and WP3, which aims to use the definition of the games done in WP2 to develop the first functional prototype of the project, to test it with teachers and children in the first iteration of the project.

Date	Version	Description	Authors
29.03.2023	1.0	Preparation of the first version of this deliverable	Lucia Vera
30.03.2023	1.1	Review and edits.	Lucia Vera, Gerardo Herrera, Ilona Heldan, Cristina Costescu

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#1. Introduction

The Empower project aims to develop different interactive games for children with neurodevelopmental disorders (NDDs) to help them to reduce their emotional and behavioural problems. For that, in WP2 we were working on the description and definition of the different games that will be included in the final platform. These games are based on two important constructs: **Executive Functions (EFs)** and **Emotion Regulation (ER)** strategies.

In WP3, the team members will use the games definition to develop a fully interactive and gamified application, that can keep the child completely engaged while the game is measuring and getting data about his/her performance, in order to feed the algorithms developed in WP4, to create a personalised intervention and self-adaptation in the games.

In this deliverable, we will explain the work done to develop the first prototype with the three selected games, using different images, videos and a link to try the first prototype application. The development was done in Unity with C# scripts and the content of the games were based on the definition done in WP2

#2. Games selected for this first prototype

In the Empower project will develop an application with nine games in these executive functions and emotional regulation areas:

Executive functions:

- 1) **Sustained Attention;**
- 2) **Working Memory;**
- 3) Cognitive Flexibility;
- 4) Delayed Gratification; and
- 5) **Behavioural Inhibition.**

Emotional regulation:

- 6) Emotion naming
- 7) Emotion Intensity level rating
- 8) Emotion Understanding
- 9) Emotion Regulation Strategies

For this first prototype, we have been working on three of the Executive Functions areas: Sustained Attention, Working Memory and Behavioural Inhibition. For the global game, we have selected an ECOFARM concept (Ecological Farm) as the common thread of the game.

In the following sections, we will describe each game's implementation.

SUSTAINED ATTENTION GAME

This game aims to measure and assess the ability to maintain the focus of attention of children with NDD in a specific task. The game has a forest as background and the main task of the student is to press the spacebar whenever a specific mushroom appears in the forest. There will be only one target, a correct mushroom and different distractors. The game has three main levels with three sub-levels each one, where we modify the distractors and the positions where the stimuli can appear, to increase the complexity of the task, as the student moves to a higher level. The activity has 60 trials in each sub-level and measures the reaction time, the total correct answers, the total incorrect answers and the correct and incorrect answers in each condition (target present and target not present).

The game has a first introduction screen, where it is possible to select the level and read the instructions:

After selecting the level, the student enters the game pressing the play button. In all the games, the student starts following a short demonstration of the game, where we give all the information about how to play with the specific game and the student has to follow a step-by-step sequence to learn to play with it. Anytime, the student can skip the demonstration and go directly to the game.

After the demonstration, the student can test the game with a reduced number of trials to check if he/she knows how to play with it. After the test is finished, the child can repeat the test again or move on to play with the game. In this case a timer starts and hits and other parameters are controlled. To start the game the child will first see a countdown indicating the real start of the game.

Inside the game, you can see, depending on the level, flowers, branches, butterflies and other types of mushrooms as distractors. The distractors used and the position of the elements will change depending on the sub-level. Higher sub-level number means a more difficult position for the target and distractors and more similar to the target distractors.

At the end of the 60 trials, the student can see a “Well done” advice to know that the game has finished. After that, the application shows the values of the recorded parameters for this task.

It is possible to see a complete video of this game in the following link:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=S3Aao6D-8wU>

WORKING MEMORY GAME

The Working Memory Game is based on the executive function related to maintaining task-relevant information during the execution of complex cognitive tasks. In this case, the student has to play in a vegetable patch where there are nine pepper plants growing. There are two tasks in this game:

1. Classify the peppers in the corresponding basket when they turn yellow, depending on the quality of the pepper. The student has to sort peppers into suitable baskets based on their characteristics. Specially, ripe peppers should be placed in one basket prepared to be sold on the market. However, if a pepper has a worm, it cannot be sold and must be placed in a separate basket. While the student is sorting, it is important to be focused on the order in which the peppers are changing their colour to yellow.
2. After the sorting task, the student has to select the peppers which turned yellow, trying to select them in the same order that they changed in the previous step.

To complete the game, the student has to perform five trials where it is possible to see a different sequence of peppers in each. There are three levels of difficulty, where we increase the quantity of peppers becoming yellow in the sequence (2, 3 or 4 depending on the level). In this game, the parameters measured are: the correct peppers classified, incorrect peppers

classified, the number of correct sequences selected and sorted, the number of correct sequences selected but not sorted, the longest sorted sequence and the mean response time.

As we mentioned before, we start the game with the instructions screen, where one can see how to play and select the desired difficulty level.

When the children press the play button, they can enter to the demonstration mode to learn how to play the game.

After the demonstration, you can play a test with two trials, to know if you learn enough to play the game correctly. At the end, you can test again until you learn how to play or you can move to play the game itself, where the application starts to control the time and the correct and incorrect responses the user does.

At the end of the game, the student can see the “Well done” advice and then the values of the parameters recorded during the game that can inform about the child's performance.

It is possible to see a complete video of this game in the following link:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IHK4uaepA8U>

BEHAVIOURAL INHIBITION GAME

The Behavioural inhibition game aims to test the ability to stop mid-task to regulate behaviour or complete a non-dominant response. In this case, the game is related to a recycling task in the garden of the farmhouse. The student has two tasks:

1. Pick up all the trash from the garden of the house.
2. Sort each item in the proper recycling bin. An item will exit from the black bin and a recycle bin lid will open. The child has to answer if the bin is the correct one or not for the specific item. In this case, the student has to inhibit his/her response due to congruent and incongruent situations. There can be a plastic bottle in a green colour and the green bin lid opened. In this case, it is an incongruent situation so that the child has to answer “No”. In another case, there can be a yellow box and the blue bin lid opened. In this case, it is a congruent situation so that the child has to answer “Yes”.

The game has three different levels, where we change the quantity of elements used in each trial. There are twelve trials, which means that the child will have to pick up and recycle twelve objects.

The parameters controlled during the game to measure the performance are: total correct answers, correct answers for congruent and incongruent, total incorrect answers, incorrect answers for congruent and incongruent, percentage of with no answer, mean response time, and mean response time for congruent and incongruent.

The first screen, as in the other games, is the instruction screen, where it is possible to select the level and read the information about how to play the game.

Then, as in the other games, a demonstration starts, and you have to follow the steps to learn how to play this game.

After the demonstration, you can play a test of the game to check your understanding of the tasks. Then you can repeat the test as many times as you want or move to play the game itself.

The game always starts with a countdown.

Then, you have to click on each trash element to pick it up. It goes automatically to the black bin.

After you pick all the trash, you have to classify it correctly. You can have congruent situations, where the recycling bin is correct and the object has a different colour from the bin. Therefore, you have to press “Yes” because it is the correct bin. The element will fly to enter the correct bin.

If you have an incongruent situation, where the bin is incorrect and the element has the same colour as the bin, you have to inhibit your immediate answer that can be yes, to indicate “No” because it is not correct. In this case, the element returns to the black bin.

At the end of all the trials, the child can see the “Well done” advice, indicating that the end of the game has been reached.

After that, it is possible to see the result screen, where all the values for the parameters registered during the game.

Results	
Total Correct Answers:	10
Correct Congruent:	5
Correct Incongruent:	5
Total Incorrect Answers:	2
Incorrect Congruent:	1
Incorrect Incongruent:	1
Percentage Trials with no answer:	0%
Mean Response Time:	3,02
Mean Response Time Congruent:	3,73
Mean Response Time Incongruent:	2,32

It is possible to see a complete video of this game in the following link:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tOijXHy31Vs>

#3. First prototype application

It is possible to download and test the prototype application from the following link:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1cIQSR-aS5HmzbEGu7CfUmtmoXrzvsBHf?usp=sharing>

#4. Hardware required

This prototype was developed using Unity for a Windows device. In this first version, you only need a computer with Windows 10 or 11, a keyboard and a mouse. A dedicated graphic card is recommended also for the next versions due to the use of 3D graphics.